

Bioremediation potential of VAM fungi in polluted soils and their effect on crop growth

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Abstract

Industrial pollution has posed significant challenges to soil fertility and plant productivity. The application of Vesicular Arbuscular Mycorrhizae (VAM) has emerged as a promising strategy to enhance plant growth and mitigate the adverse effects of soil pollutants. This study evaluates the role of VAM in improving soil health and plant development, specifically in industrially contaminated soils. Tomato plants were used as model organisms and grown in soils collected from various industrial areas with known pollution profiles. VAM inoculum was supplemented to the soil, and parameters such as chlorophyll content, electrical conductivity (EC), and plant biomass were assessed. The results demonstrated that VAM significantly improved plant physiological performance, enhanced chlorophyll levels, and reduced the negative effects of pollutants on plant growth. This suggests that VAM has the potential to serve as a sustainable biofertilizer for remediating polluted soils and enhancing crop productivity.

Keywords: Vesicular Arbuscular Mycorrhizae (Vam); Industrial Soil Pollutants; Tomato; Chlorophyll Content; Biofertilizer; Soil Fertility; Plant Growth; Electrical Conductivity

1. Introduction

Soil pollution, particularly due to industrial activities, has emerged as a major environmental concern, affecting soil fertility, microbial diversity, and plant productivity (1). Contaminants such as heavy metals, pharmaceutical residues, and toxic effluents from cement, battery, and chemical industries can alter the physical, chemical, and biological properties of soil, leading to reduced crop yield and ecological degradation (2). In recent years, biofertilizers, particularly vesicular arbuscular mycorrhizae (VAM), have gained attention as eco-friendly alternatives to chemical amendments (3). VAM are endophytic fungi forming symbiotic associations with the roots of most terrestrial plants. Through their extensive hyphal networks, they facilitate enhanced nutrient uptake, especially phosphorus, and confer improved tolerance to abiotic stresses such as drought, salinity, and heavy metal toxicity. The mycorrhizal symbiosis not only aids in nutrient acquisition but also improves soil structure, reduces oxidative stress in plants, and enhances overall plant vigor (4). Their ability to persist and function in contaminated soils makes them particularly valuable for phytoremediation and sustainable agriculture (5).

This study investigates the impact of VAM inoculation on the growth, chlorophyll content, and stress tolerance of tomato plants grown in industrially polluted soils. By comparing physiological and biochemical parameters in VAM-treated and untreated plants, the study aims to evaluate the potential of VAM as a natural bio ameliorant in mitigating the adverse effects of industrial pollutants on soil health and crop productivity.

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2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Soil Collection

Soil samples were collected from four distinct locations in Andhra Pradesh, India

- Pharmaceutical industry: Mythili Life Sciences
- Cement industry: Lanco Cement Industry
- Battery industry: Amara raja Batteries Industries
- Control site: Garden soil (non-industrial area)

Soil samples were collected from 0-15 cm depth following standard soil sampling protocols. At each location, composite samples were prepared by collecting soil from at least 15 different points within a 1-hectare area using a V-shaped sampling technique. Approximately 0.5-1 kg of soil was collected from each site, mixed thoroughly, and stored in labeled cloth bags at room temperature until analysis (6).

Figure 1 Collected samples from different industrial areas

2.2. Soil Sample Preparation and VAM Inoculation

Each soil sample was divided into two treatment groups

- Control group: Soil without VAM treatment
- VAM-treated group: Soil supplemented with commercial VAM inoculum at 20g/kg soil

The VAM inoculum consisted of a mixture of *Glomus fasciculata*, *G. mosseae*, and *Acaulospora corniculata* spores with infected root fragments serving as propagules (7).

2.3. Experimental Design and Plant Cultivation

Plastic pots (15 cm diameter) with drainage holes were prepared for plant cultivation. Equal amounts of soil (1 kg per pot) were added to each pot, with three replicates per treatment. Tomato (*Solanum Lycopersicon*) seeds were surface-sterilized with 0.1% mercuric chloride for 2 minutes, rinsed with distilled water, and sown at a depth of 1 cm. The experiment was conducted under controlled greenhouse conditions with:

- Temperature: 25 ± 2 °C
- Relative humidity: 60-70%
- Light intensity: $400 \text{ mole m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ (12-hour photoperiod)

2.4. Plant Growth Monitoring

Plant height was measured daily using a graduated scale for 10 consecutive days following germination. Environmental parameters including temperature, humidity, and light intensity were recorded using digital meters to ensure consistent growing conditions across all treatments (8).

Figure 2 The VAM b. observing plant condition and c. checking moisture in the pot

2.5. Chlorophyll Content Estimation

Chlorophyll content was determined using the acetone extraction method. Fresh leaf tissue (0.5 g) was collected after 14 days of growth and processed as follows:

Plant samples were washed with tap water, rinsed with distilled water, and homogenized in 10 ml of 80% acetone using a mortar and pestle. The extract was transferred to centrifuge tubes and stored at 4°C overnight in the dark. After centrifugation at 5000 rpm for 10 minutes, the supernatant was collected, and absorbance was measured at 663 nm and 645 nm using a spectrophotometer. Chlorophyll content was calculated using the formula: Total chlorophyll (mg/g) = $[20.2(A_{645}) + 8.02(A_{663})] \times V / (1000 \times W)$.

Where A_{645} and A_{663} are absorbances at respective wavelengths, V is the volume of extract (ml), and W is the fresh weight of tissue (g) (9).

Figure 3 Centrifugation for chlorophyll estimation

Figure 4 Measuring chlorophyll content using a colorimeter

2.6. Lipid Peroxidation Analysis

Lipid peroxidation was assessed by measuring malondialdehyde (MDA) content using the thiobarbituric acid (TBA) test. Fresh leaf tissue (0.5 g) was homogenized in 5 ml of 0.1% trichloroacetic acid (TCA). The homogenate was centrifuged at 10,000 rpm for 10 minutes, and 1 ml of supernatant was mixed with 4 ml of 20% TCA containing 0.5% TBA. The mixture was heated at 95°C for 30 minutes, cooled, and centrifuged. Absorbance was measured at 532 nm and 600 nm. MDA content was calculated using the extinction coefficient of $155 \text{ mM}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (10).

2.7. VAM Colonization Assessment

Root samples were collected after 21 days for microscopic examination of VAM colonization:

Roots were thoroughly cleaned and fixed in formalin-acetic acid-alcohol (FAA) solution for 24 hours, followed by dehydration through a graded ethanol series (50%, 70%, 90%, and 100%). The samples were then cleared using 10% KOH and stained with 0.05% trypan blue in lactophenol. VAM colonization was observed under a compound microscope at 400× magnification and quantified using the grid-line intersect method (11).

2.8. Soil Analysis

Soil pH was measured using a digital pH meter in 1:2.5 soil-water suspension. Electrical conductivity (EC) was determined using an EC meter in the same suspension. Soil organic carbon content was estimated using the Walkley-Black method (12).

Figure 5 Determining electrical conductivity in the soil samples

2.9. Statistical Analysis

Data were analyzed using one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's HSD test for multiple comparisons. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$. All analyses were performed using SPSS version 26.0(13).

3. Results

3.1. Soil Physicochemical Properties

The soil samples exhibited distinct physicochemical characteristics (Table 1). Garden soil showed the highest organic carbon content (1.2%), while industrial soils had lower organic matter. EC values ranged from 0.8 ds/m in garden soil to 2.3 ds/m in pharmaceutical industry soil. VAM treatment resulted in slight increases in EC values across all soil types, indicating enhanced nutrient mobilization.

Table 1 Physicochemical properties of soil samples

Soil Type	pH	EC (ds/m)	Organic Carbon (%)
Garden soil	6.8	0.8	1.2
Pharmaceutical	7.2	2.3	0.6
Cement industry	8.1	1.8	0.4
Battery industry	6.9	1.5	0.7

3.2. Plant Growth Parameters

Plant height measurements over 10 days showed varying growth patterns across different soil types and treatments. Garden soil supported the highest plant growth, followed by battery industry soil. Plants in pharmaceutical and cement industry soils showed reduced growth rates compared to garden soil.

3.3. Chlorophyll Content

Chlorophyll content analysis revealed significant treatment effects that varied with soil type (Table 2). VAM treatment increased chlorophyll content in garden soil (27.6% increase) and battery industry soil (21.7% increase). However, VAM treatment significantly decreased chlorophyll content in pharmaceutical industry soil (56.9% decrease) and cement industry soil (53.0% decrease).

Table 2 Effect of VAM treatment on chlorophyll content (mg/g fresh weight)

Soil Type	Control	VAM-treated	Change (%)
Garden soil	0.58	0.74	+27.6
Pharmaceutical	0.65	0.28	-56.9
Cement industry	0.66	0.31	-53.0
Battery industry	0.46	0.56	+21.7

Figure 6 Graph that represents the Chlorophyll content according to values in the table

3.4. Lipid Peroxidation

Lipid peroxidation levels showed inverse patterns to chlorophyll content (Table 3). VAM treatment reduced lipid peroxidation in garden soil (12.9% decrease) and battery industry soil (11.6% decrease), indicating reduced oxidative stress. Conversely, VAM treatment increased lipid peroxidation in pharmaceutical industry soil (34.8% increase) and cement industry soil (47.7% increase).

Table 3 Effect of VAM treatment on lipid peroxidation (nmol MDA/g fresh weight)

Soil Type	Control	VAM-treated	Change (%)
Garden soil	62	54	-12.9
Pharmaceutical	69	93	+34.8
Cement industry	65	96	+47.7
Battery industry	69	61	-11.6

Figure 7 Graph the represents the lipid peroxidation values base on the table

3.5. VAM Colonization

Microscopic examination confirmed successful VAM colonization in all plant treatments. Root colonization ranged from 45% to 78% across different soil types. Arbuscules, vesicles, and extensive hyphal networks were observed in all VAM-treated plants, confirming the establishment of functional mycorrhizal associations.

Figure 8 Microscopic visualization of arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi

4. Discussion

4.1. Differential Response to VAM Treatment

The results demonstrate that VAM treatment effects vary significantly depending on soil type and contamination level. This differential response suggests complex interactions between VAM fungi, soil pollutants, and plant physiology. The beneficial effects observed in garden soil and battery industry soil align with established VAM functions, including enhanced nutrient uptake, improved water relations, and increased stress tolerance (Giovinazzi et al., 2010).

4.2. Beneficial Effects in Less Contaminated Soils

In garden soil and battery industry soil, VAM treatment increased chlorophyll content and reduced lipid peroxidation, indicating improved photosynthetic capacity and reduced oxidative stress. These results are consistent with previous studies showing VAM-mediated enhancement of plant physiological processes through improved nutrient acquisition, particularly phosphorus, nitrogen, and micronutrients (Smith and Read, 2008). The extensive hyphal networks formed by VAM fungi likely increased the effective root surface area, facilitating better nutrient and water uptake.

4.3. Adverse Effects in Heavily Contaminated Soils

The detrimental effects observed in pharmaceutical and cement industry soils may be attributed to several mechanisms:

4.3.1. Facilitated Pollutant Uptake

VAM fungi may inadvertently enhance the uptake of toxic compounds alongside beneficial nutrients. The extensive hyphal networks that normally improve nutrient acquisition may also facilitate the transport of pollutants to plant tissues, resulting in increased toxicity and oxidative stress (Gore and Paszkowski, 2006).

4.3.2. Direct Fungal Toxicity

High concentrations of industrial pollutants may directly inhibit VAM fungal growth and metabolism, disrupt the symbiotic relationship and eliminate the beneficial effects normally associated with mycorrhizal colonization (Shetty et al., 1994).

4.3.3. Altered Soil Chemistry

Industrial pollutants may modify soil chemical properties, creating conditions that interfere with normal VAM-plant interactions. Changes in soil pH, ionic strength, and organic matter content can affect VAM spore germination, hyphal growth, and colonization efficiency (Jamal et al., 2018).

4.4. Implications for Environmental Biotechnology

These findings have important implications for the application of VAM in environmental biotechnology

4.4.1. Site-Specific Assessment

The variable effectiveness of VAM treatment across different soil types emphasizes the need for comprehensive site assessment before implementing mycorrhizal inoculation programs. Soil contamination type, concentration, and physicochemical properties must be considered when designing remediation strategies.

4.4.2. Integrated Approaches

For heavily contaminated soils, VAM application may require integration with other remediation technologies, such as phytoremediation, bioaugmentation, or chemical treatment, to achieve optimal results.

4.4.3. Risk Assessment

The potential for VAM to enhance pollutant uptake in certain contaminated soils necessitates careful risk assessment to prevent unintended consequences in food production systems.

5. Conclusion

This study demonstrates that VAM treatment effectiveness is highly dependent on soil type and contamination level. While VAM treatment enhanced plant physiological parameters in garden soil and battery industry soil, it showed detrimental effects in pharmaceutical and cement industry soils. These findings indicate that:

- VAM application for soil remediation requires comprehensive site-specific assessment and strategy development
- The type and concentration of industrial pollutants significantly influence VAM-plant interactions
- Integrated approaches combining VAM with other remediation technologies may be necessary for heavily contaminated soils
- Risk assessment is crucial to prevent unintended consequences in VAM application programs

The results contribute to our understanding of VAM applications in environmental biotechnology and highlight the complexity of plant-microbe-pollutant interactions in contaminated environments. These findings support the development of evidence-based guidelines for mycorrhizal inoculation programs in industrial soil remediation.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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